

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Scientific and non-scientific
- events, conferences and journals -

D9.8 Printed Materials with project Results

*Authors: Luisa Ardizzone, Jelena Mazaj
CESIE, Via Roma 94 – 90133 Palermo, Italy*

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

Document Information

Grant Agreement #:	822688
Project Title:	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
Project Acronym:	RAISD
Project Start Date:	1 st February, 2019
Work package:	WP9 Dissemination and communication
Deliverable:	D9.8 Printed materials with the project results
	Brochures and reports for the project, papers in conferences and journals.
Related task(s):	T9.2 Community involvement: Coordination of participation in events, conferences and journals.
Lead Organisation:	CESIE, Italy
Submission date:	Month 41
Dissemination Level:	Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (Notes)
09/01/2022	CESIE	All partners	V0
30/05/2022	All partners	CESIE	V1
30/06/2022	CESIE	All partners	V2 Final

This Report is published under an [Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license [CC BY-SA].

Table of content

Executive Summary	5
1 RAISD Conference	6
1.1 Conference AGENDA	7
1.2 Key-note speakers	10
2 Journal Articles	14
Responsible research and innovation (RRI) as a driving force for change in corporate communication: New forms of governance and participatory structures.....	14
Social Care for the Migrant Population in Spain: Needs and Strengths of Organisations during the COVID-19 Pandemic and Infodemic	15
Layers of confinement: Asylum seekers experiences of isolation in Finnish reception centres	16
Acts of participation: Asylum seekers' struggle for inclusion in Finland.....	17
The Effectiveness of a Training Program based on Psychosocial Support in improving Family Empowerment level among Refugees in Jordan.....	18
The Effectiveness of a Training Program Based on Health Education to Improve Health Empowerment Level among Refugees in Jordan.....	19
The Effectiveness of a Psychosocial Support-Based Program in Raising Legal Empowerment among Refugees in Jordan.....	20
The Effectiveness of a counselling program based on psychosocial support in raising the level of economic empowerment of Syrian refugees	21
3 Books	23
Fragments of Exile.....	23
Educational innovation practices facing current challenges of the university: service learning, creativity and approaching professional reality	25
4 Conference Proceedings	27
Educational innovation in European projects: Delving into forced migrations via organizing an international workshop.....	27
Selective education experiences with highly vulnerable groups. Pilot experience in Palermo, Italy.....	28
Deconstruction of narratives and identification of hate speech	31
Webdoc Reflections/Webdoc Espejismos.....	32
Participatory cinema and migration	34
Using collaborative methodology and communication for redefining and assessing new attention and inclusion strategies for forcible displaced people	35
Integrating forced migrants in the research and communication project using the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation.	37

Rethinking vulnerabilities via intersectional approaches to migration contexts, intercultural and interpersonal communication 39

Rethinking the impact of media discourse on migration and forced migration during the pandemic..... 41

Co-design of an Inclusive Training in Digital Skills with Refugee Women..... 43

Embedding gender approach in international research 45

Frames of participation: Reception centre professionals’ perceptions on asylum seekers’ participation in Fi 47

Also men should have the right to flee from violence and persecution..... 49

Vulnerability Profiling and Dynamics of Monitoring as an Advocacy Approach: Case of RAISD Project..... 49

Addressing the challenge of forced displacement 51

5 Grey literature (not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g. reports).....52

6 TAIS Specific publications

“ALL you can LEARN” (AUCL) 55

“ALL you can LEARN” Trainees’ Diary 57

“ALL you can TEACH” Educational Resources for Professionals in the field of MIGRATION 58

Vulnerable refugees. Training exercises based on true stories 59

7 Discussion Events.....60

H2020 National workshop “Challenge 6: Europe in a changing world”, organized by FECYT (Foundation for Science and Technology) 60

RESCUE EU Project conference in Rome, organized by UNIMED 61

Action Research and Unique Approaches in Refugee Studies – Horizon 2020 RAISD Project 62

RAISD Project Presentation at UNIMED SubNetwork Migration 62

Institute of Knowledge Technology (ITC) Conference..... 63

RAISD (Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Forcibly Displaced People) 64

8 Materials for dissemination activities65

About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

The sole responsibility of this publication lies with the author.

The European Union is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Coordinator contact:

Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain.

t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es grasia.fdi.ucm.es

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fdi.ucm.es

Executive Summary

This document reports about the achieved results under *D9.8 Printed Materials with project Results: Scientific and non-scientific journals and the participation in events, conferences*. The outcomes are related to “Task 9.2 Community involvement” that includes the Coordination of publications of academic articles in scientific journals/bulletins and participation in discussion events (e.g. presentations in scientific conferences and workshops); also, to be considered are printed materials with the project results for dissemination activities (e.g. brochures, leaflets, conference materials).

This deliverable provides information about the RAISD publications produced during the lifespan of the project. It gives information about the authors, the journals or books they were published in and the identification numbers. Also links to the publications are included. Finally, this deliverable presents publication and conference activities planned to take place after the project's ending and that intend to contribute to a broader uptake of the project's results in the field of research and innovation studies, as well as to promote the RAISD tailored attention inclusion approach.

Find below a summary of events and publications presented in this report - RAISD Project has produced or participated in:

- [1 project Final Conference](#)
- [8 Journal articles \(4 of them have been selected by indexed scientific journals\)](#)
- [2 Books or book chapters](#)
- [16 Conference proceedings](#)
- [26 Grey Literature \(project deliverables in Green Open Access\)](#)
- [4 TAIS specific publications](#)
- [6 Discussion events](#)

1 RAISD Conference

The RAISD International Conference “*Tailoring Research and inclusion Strategies for vulnerable migrant contexts*” was held on Tuesday 17th and Wednesday 18th May 2022 Palermo, Italy].

Date and time	Tuesday 17/05/2022, 10h00 – 17h00 Wednesday 18/05/2022, 09h30 – 13h00		
Venue	Real Albergo dei Poveri C.so Calatafimi, 217 – Palermo, Italy		
Agenda/Follow up	https://raisd-h2020.eu/final-conference		
Streaming	DAY 1 Morning: https://fb.watch/d5yZHNVMdY/ Afternoon: https://fb.watch/d5yTk1j3j3/		
	DAY 2: https://fb.watch/d5yNMDI6wJ/		
Registrations	https://raisd-international-conference.eventbrite.it		
Call for Experts	https://raisd-h2020.eu/final-conference/call		
Evaluation	https://forms.gle/P8DwYPa8SFFfR21x7		
Dissemination	Press-Releases, e-Newsletter, social media campaign.		
Languages	English (availability of Italian simultaneous translation).		
Participation	Total	DAY 1	DAY 2
Key-note speakers	3	2	1
N. individual talks	4	3	1
N. Panels	6	3	3
Attendees	60	56	39

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fdu.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

1.1 Conference AGENDA

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/final-conference/>

Moderator of the Conference - Giovanni Barbieri, Migration Unit - CESIE

DAY 1: Tuesday 17/05/2022	
09:30 - 10:00	Registration
10:00 - 10:15	Welcome and Opening <p style="text-align: right;"><i>Vito La Fata, President CESIE (Italy)</i> <i>Jelena Mazaj, Higher Education and Research Unit coordinator CESIE (Italy)</i> <i>Rubén Fuentes, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i></p>
10:15 - 10:30	Introduction of RAISD project: ‘Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced’ <i>Rubén Fuentes, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i>
10:30 – 11:00	Key-note \\\ Debra Kayembe – Human rights activist and Rector, University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom) <i>“Cultural interference is paramount to providing positive support for the vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people”</i>
11:00 – 11:15	Institutional greetings - Municipality of Palermo Leoluca Orlando, Mayor of the City of Palermo
11:15 - 11:30	Coffee break
11:30 -11:45	RAISD methodology and practices : Responsible Research and Innovation, Action Research, Socio-ecological Model <i>Noelia García Castillo, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i>
11:45 - 12:30	Panel 1: Vulnerability profiling among Forcibly Displaced People ‘ Vulnerability Profiles vs Vulnerability Contexts’ Moderator: <i>Nezih Orhon, Anadolu University (Turkey)</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Noelia García Castillo, Universidad Complutense de Madrid - Spain</i> ▪ <i>Soad Ibrahim, CESIE - Italy</i> ▪ <i>Antti Kivijärvi, Helsinki University - Finland</i> ▪ <i>Borbála Benedek, Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants - Hungary</i> ▪ <i>Tayfun Dalkılıç and Elif Akçakaya, Anadolu University - Turkey</i> ▪ <i>Anas AlSobeh and Zayed Hammad, Yarmouk University - Jordan</i>
12:30 - 13:15	Panel 2: Research for Change : Gender, Forced Migration and Vulnerabilities

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
 t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fdu.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

	<p><i>Moderator: Liisa Hänninen, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Naima Ahmad Al-Husban, “Young female refugees’ education: from policies to pedagogical practices” ▪ Manuela Ramos, Nancy Njoka “Contributions of women refugees to livelihoods in urban displacements in Nairobi, Kenya” ▪ Aline Saraiva Leao Lima, “The precariousness of refugee camps”
<p>Lunch</p>	
<p>14:30 - 15:15</p>	<p>Video-documentary: Refugees and people from host communities share their experiences through letters, stories, tales and poems <i>Rubén Fuentes, Noelia García Castillo and Liisa Hänninen, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i></p>
	<p>Panel 3: Responsiveness through TAIS (Tailored Attention and Inclusion Practices) <i>Moderator: Béla Soltész, Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants (Hungary)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Liisa Hänninen, Universidad Complutense de Madrid ▪ Luisa Ardizzone, CESIE ▪ Martta Myllylä, Helsinki University - Finland ▪ Bernadette Daragics, Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants - Hungary ▪ Deniz Kılıç and Duygu Keçeli, Anadolu University - Turkey ▪ Kefya Khoder, Yarmouk University - Jordan
<p>16:45 – 17:00</p>	<p>Closure</p>

DAY 2: Wednesday 18/05/2022

<p>09:00 – 9:30</p>	<p>Registration</p>
<p>09:30 – 09:45</p>	<p>Welcome and Opening</p>
<p>09:45- 10:15</p>	<p>Key-note \\\ Maria Jesus Vega - UNHCR spokesperson (Spain) <i>“Global Compact on Refugees: the difference we all can make in refugees’ lives”</i></p>
	<p>Panel 4: Action-Research Units, Quintuple Helix Representation. Importance of collaboration between local inclusion actors and actions <i>Moderator: Raniero Chelli, UNIMED - Mediterranean Universities Union (Italy)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Noelia García Castillo, Universidad Complutense de Madrid - Spain ▪ Cloè Saint-Nom, Rights and Justice Unit Coordinator CESIE - Italy ▪ Martta Myllylä, Helsinki University - Finland ▪ Bernadette Daragics, Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants - Hungary ▪ Nezhir Orhon, Anadolu University - Turkey ▪ Amani Shatnawi, Yarmouk University - Jordan
<p>11:00 - 11:15</p>	<p>Capacity Building: overview of the RAISD Training Resources for inclusion through strategies tailored upon the vulnerability context of Forcibly Displaced People <i>Emilia Stoduto, UNIMED - Mediterranean Universities Union (Italy)</i></p>

11:15 - 11:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:30 - 12:15	<p>Panel 5: Exploring CRIOS: Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software Tool <i>Moderator: Rubén Fuentes-Fernández, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i> <i>Rubén Fuentes-Fernández, Universidad Complutense de Madrid - Spain</i> <i>Ahmad Sawalhah, Yarmouk University - Jordan</i> <i>Fadi Yamout, Lebanese International University - Lebanon</i></p>
12:15 - 12:45	<p>Panel 6: RAISD Observatory. Finalizing today for tomorrow <i>Liisa Hänninen, Universidad Complutense de Madrid (Spain)</i></p>
12:45 - 13:00	<p>Creating urban space for connections and collaboration <i>Fabio Massimo Lo Verde – University of Palermo (Italy)</i></p>
13:00 – 14:30	<p>Conference Closure <i>Networking Lunch</i></p>

1.2 Key-note speakers

17/05/2022 Institutional greetings - Municipality of Palermo. Council of Cultures#migration

[Leoluca Orlando, Mayor of the City of Palermo](#)

Believing that people have the right to move in search of a better life, Mayor Orlando is welcoming migrants to the City of Palermo. All migrants in Palermo are considered Palermitani (citizens of Palermo) and can access education, medical care and have the right to work after two months residence in the city. Migrant participation in Palermo's politics is encouraged through the Council of Cultures, an advisory body proposed by Mayor Orlando and established by the City of Palermo. The council consists of 21 migrants from different geographical regions, elected by and representing city residents. Palermo also provides young, unaccompanied migrants with tutors that have been provided with training, legal counselling, and the ability to help migrants in their interactions with the authorities. While the mayor is not able to grant permanent residence in Italy, to enhance their feeling of belonging, migrants are invited to honorary citizenship ceremonies. Mayor Orlando also makes small but important gestures of welcome such as officially participating in all religious celebrations of the city's communities, wearing the tricolour band symbolising his representation of the state to enhance the feeling for event participants of being part of Palermo's community.

17/05/2022 Key-note \\\ Debra Kayembe – Human rights activist and Rector, University of Edinburgh (United Kingdom)

>>>> *“Cultural interference is paramount to providing positive support for the vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people”*

Ms Debra Kayembe was called to the Congolese Bar Association in 2000, and has been a member of the Institute of Translation and Interpreting from 2010-2020. In 2016 she joined the language services of the office of the prosecutor at the International Criminal Court and the International Criminal Court Bar Association (ICCBA). Debra served as Scottish Refugee Council board member from 2013 – 2016. She also joined the Royal Society of Edinburgh/Young Academy of Scotland representing refugee minorities, and has a seat as an expert lawyer to the RSE Working Group for Africa. In 2017 Debra founded the charity Full Options.

In August 2019, history was made at the Royal Society of Edinburgh, when Debra became the first African to have her portrait erected at the wall of the society honouring her achievements and contributions to the Scottish Society.

In July 2020, Debra launched the Freedom Walk campaign – a civil rights movement which aims to lobby and campaign on behalf of citizens by promoting social reforms, racial justice

and community harmony. Debora is also petitioning to the Scottish Parliament in favour of anti-racist education in Scotland. On the 3rd of February 2021, Debora Kayembe become the first person of Colour to be elected as Rector of the University of Edinburgh in 437 years and the 3rd Women to hold the position.

18/05/2022 Key-note \\\ Maria Jesus Vega - UNHCR spokesperson (Spain)

>>> “Global Compact on Refugees: the difference we all can make in refugees’ lives”

María Jesús Vega is currently spokesperson for UNHCR in Spain and responsible for the Communications Department of the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees in the country. She studied Social Work at the Complutense University of Madrid and broadened her studies with a Fulbright grant in USA.

Vega has been for 25 years developing her professional career in the refugee field starting her work with the Red Cross, the International Rescue Committee and UNHCR. Within the UN Refugee Agency she has work in the field of protection, political incidence, family reunification, unaccompanied and separated minors, resettlement, repatriation and donor relations. She has become familiar with UNHCR operations in countries such as Colombia, Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, Ethiopia, Tunisia or Jordan and Central America. She is part of the Emergency Team of the UN Refugee Agency.

17/05/2022 [Research for Change](#): Gender, Forced Migration and Vulnerabilities

Believing in young researchers' competence, this panel celebrates the winners of the INTERNATIONAL YOUTH WORKSHOP "RESEARCH FOR CHANGE- GENDER, FORCED MIGRATION AND VULNERABILITIES" organised in April 2021.

The focus is on practical proposals that help to understand and transform problems experienced by forced migrants, especially women, and to foster an efficient reception and promote a strong hosting system, as well as to develop innovative actions that contribute to better attention and inclusion strategies for forcibly displaced people.

- **Naima Ahmad Al-Husban, "Young female refugees' education: from policies to pedagogical practices"**

Naima Al-Husban is an associate professor at Arab Open University- Jordan, she is interested in working with refugees, she has an experience in this field by working as a volunteer in HOPES project that has been funded by EU, and helped several young female refugees to study at universities, and she is the focal point of the international project about education in emergencies led by Geneva University. She has several publications in the field of education in emergencies, especially refugee student' perceptions to certain issue like open learning, and she is so interested in investigating further issues behind school- age female refugees dropping out, professional development of teachers of refugees.

- **Manuela Ramos, Nancy Njoka "Contributions of women refugees to livelihoods in urban displacements in Nairobi, Kenya"**

Manuela Ramos is a young development advocate with expertise in communications of human rights and migration issues. She has a MSc background of IDS and Communication studies at Roskilde University and a Bachelor's Degree in Journalism at the University of Zaragoza. She currently holds the position of Assistant Editor of WIPO Magazine, at World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), in Geneva, Switzerland, coordinating the World IP Day global awareness campaign.

Nancy is a human rights Lawyer and an international development professional with focus and interest in communication for development, forced displacement and migration. She holds a Master of Science in International development studies and Communication from Roskilde University in Denmark and a Bachelor of Laws from University of Nairobi, Kenya. Currently, she is working in project management for the Danish Arab Partnership Program supporting civic engagement and political participation among the youths in the Middle East and North African region.

- **Aline Saraiva Leão Lima, "The precariousness of refugee camps"**

Aline Saraiva Leão Lima, a Brazilian architecture student at Department of Architecture and Urbanism (DAU) at the Pontifical Catholic University of Rio de Janeiro (PUC-Rio) and member of the Humanitarian Architecture Laboratory (Lab.AH), of PUC-Rio. Nowadays, she wants to study how architecture can help with forced displacement and refugee camps in Latin America and the Caribbean context.

Scholarships for 5 external Stakeholders

Financial support from the H2020 Programme to attend the RAISD International Conference

Deadline for submissions 20th April 2022

<https://raisd-h2020.eu/final-conference/call/>

International External Stakeholders in the field of migration are invited to apply for the financial support from the H2020 Programme to attend the RAISD International Conference.

This kind of funding is provided for 5 (five) actors that commit to further exploit the RAISD Results into own research and/or practices for the inclusion of highly vulnerable people in forced displacement.

If selected, the candidates will need to provide evidence of knowledge multiplication-exploitation activities implemented in their own local context after max. 2 months after the event in Palermo (e.g. publication of scientific article, local projects/workshops implementation, media campaigning and alike).

This call is open to actors and stakeholders of the following communities:

- Scientific Community (Researchers who are at an early stage of their careers, either doing their PhD or having their MSc or MA just completed)
- Educational Community (Training centres, VET providers)
- Policy Makers (Authorities, Agencies and Institutions)
- Business and Industry (including micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), Job centres)
- Civil Society (Grassroots, CSO, NGO)
- Media (press, radio, television, influencer)
- Other interested parties.

The all-inclusive cost of the conference (travel, accommodation and subsistence costs) will be covered for a maximum amount of € 800. The participants will initially have to bear all costs, the actual amount spent will be repaid via bank transfer after the conference upon presentation of all necessary supporting documents.

Candidates are requested to:

- Prepare and upload a short Europass CV [max. 2 pages]
- Prepare and upload a 300-word motivation letter explaining your interest and potential exploitation plan
- Fill out the [application form](#) [CV and motivation letter can be uploaded in the application form!]

For more information please contact press@raisd-h2020.eu

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fducm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

2 Journal Articles

Responsible research and innovation (RRI) as a driving force for change in corporate communication: New forms of governance and participatory structures

Partner(s)	Complutense University of Madrid, Spain.
Author(s)	Noelia García-Castillo http://orcid.org/0000-0001-5875-0195 ; Tamara Bueno-Doral http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2954-1519 ; Liisa-Irene Hänninen http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8567-4201
Place	Spain
Year	2020
Type	Journal Article
Title	El Profesional de la Información > International Journal on Information and Communication
Number, date	Vol. 29 Núm. 3 (2020): Relaciones Públicas.
Publisher	El Profesional de la Información > International Journal on Information and Communication
DOI	https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2020.may.13
ISBN/ISSN	e-ISSN 1699-2407; ISSN 1386-2407; CODEN: PINFF2 https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2020.may.13
Language	English
Keywords	Responsible Research and Innovation, RRI, Corporate Social Responsibility, CSR, Corporate communication, Organizational communication, Innovation, Stakeholders, Governance, Citizen participation.
Open Access	Gold Open Access
Peer-reviewed	YES
Link(s)	https://revista.profesionaldelainformacion.com/index.php/EPI/article/view/epi.2020.may.13
Abstract	
<p>Nowadays, the emerging discipline of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) has great acceptance among the scientific community in general. Nevertheless, its presence in social sciences has not reached the development obtained in other disciplines. Studies describing RRI application to areas such as business, and more specifically, corporate communication, are scarce. The objective of this study is to show the possible application of the principles of the emerging RRI discipline to business and corporate communication, as well as the main barriers</p>	

and benefits that could arise. For this, we provide a documentary review of the existing literature and an analysis of fifteen semi-structured interviews with Spanish experts in RRI. Likewise, the article addresses the relationship between RRI and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). As a main conclusion, we observe that RRI has the potential to become the driving force for new forms of governance and communication, but requires changes in corporate philosophy and performance, as it is a bottom-up participatory movement, promoted by the objective of a sustainable society for future generations. In addition, this study represents a contribution to the current discussion regarding the application of the principles and processes of RRI beyond the academic field.

Social Care for the Migrant Population in Spain: Needs and Strengths of Organisations during the COVID-19 Pandemic and Infodemic

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Tamara Bueno-Doral http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2954-1519 María Lara https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6414-8034 Noelia García Castillo https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5875-0195
Year	2021
Type	Journal article
Title	International Journal of Migration, Health and Social Care
Publisher	Emerald
DOI	DOI 10.1108/IJMHS-10-2020-0097
ISBN/ISSN	ISSN: 1747-9894
Language	English
Keywords	Migration, Social care, Third sector, Refugees, COVID-19, Good practices, Migrant population
Open Access	Gold Open Access
Peer-reviewed	Yes
Link(s)	https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJMHS-10-2020-0097/full/html#abstract
Abstract	

Purpose: In the past months, the authors have experienced an exceptional global situation that especially affects the most vulnerable population. This paper aims to analyse the needs, strengths and good practices of the organisations that have continued to study with the migrant population during the health crisis. The main objective was to determine how the health, social and communication crisis has affected the management of the organisation itself, the communications with its direct beneficiaries, the communications with the rest of society, as well as the perception that organisations specialised in migration have about how media has communicated the information of COVID-19 and migrant population.

Design/methodology/approach: The authors have circulated a questionnaire with open questions that covered the four dimensions previously mentioned.

Findings: The results show the analysis of the answers of 11 of the most important national and international organisations in the field of migration and refuge that operate in Spain.

Originality/value: Key issues have emerged related not only to the principal management concerns, internal digital communication, the adaptability of external communication and the major effort required to provide information about migration but also to innovative good practices. That other third sector organisations focussed on migration will be able to apply in the future and in other geographic areas.

Layers of confinement: Asylum seekers experiences of isolation in Finnish reception centres

Partner(s)	University of Helsinki, Finland
Author(s)	Antti Kivijärvi & Martta Myllylä
Place	Finland
Year	Will be published in 2022 (accepted)
Type	Journal article
Title of Journal	Journal of Immigrant and Refugee Studies
Publisher	Taylor & Francis
Language	English
Keywords	Reception center, asylum seekers, qualitative interviews, confinement, inductive approach
Open Access	Gold
Peer-reviewed	Yes
Link(s)	https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/wimm20/current
Abstract	

The control function of reception centers hinders asylum seekers' settlement to their host communities. Even though open accommodation centers compose the majority of the European reception system, few studies have comprehensively analyzed their controlling aspects from the asylum seeker perspective. In this article, we examine asylum seekers' experiences of confinement in Finnish reception centers by using semi-structured and individual interviews (n=28). We identified three "layers" of confinement in asylum seekers' accounts: spatial, service-based, and communicative. Together, these permeable but overlapping and accumulative layers define asylum seekers' experiences by hampering their efforts to participate in local communities and reducing their autonomy.

Acts of participation: Asylum seekers' struggle for inclusion in Finland

Partner(s)	University of Helsinki, Finland
Author(s)	Antti Kivijärvi & Martta Myllylä & Mervi Pantti
Place	Finland
Type	Journal article
Title of Journal	Submitted to Journal of Ethnic and Migration Studies
Publisher	Taylor & Francis
Keywords	Asylum seekers, participation, agency, reception centres, qualitative interviews
Open Access	Gold
Peer-reviewed	Yes
Link(s)	https://www.tandfonline.com/toc/cjms20/current

Abstract

Asylum seekers are separated from the host society by the legislation and institutional practices of the reception system. Waiting period in reception centres is often characterised by confinement, passivity and lack of meaningful activities. Notwithstanding their precarious and disempowering situation, asylum seekers may engage in meaningful action and take part in community activities while waiting. In the context of the Finnish reception system, we employ the concept of 'participatory act' to analyse the ways in which asylum seekers aim for inclusion through various everyday practices and social and institutional engagements. By drawing on the qualitative analysis of individual interviews (n=28) conducted with asylum seekers in 2019, the article examines asylum seekers' participatory acts and the social spheres these acts take place. The results show how, despite the scarcity of political activism, asylum seekers are able to shape their living conditions in subtle ways instead of merely accommodating to them.

The Effectiveness of a Training Program based on Psychosocial Support in improving Family Empowerment level among Refugees in Jordan

Partner(s)	Yarmouk university
Author(s)	أحمد الشريفين فايز محاميد أماني شطناوي أنس الصباح ايمان المفلح أمينة مقدادي Ahmad al-sharifin Fayez Mahamid Amani Shatnawi Anas Al-Sobeh Eman Almifleh Amna Migdady
Title	فاعلية برنامج مستند للدعم النفسي الاجتماعي في رفع مستوى التمكين الأسري لدى اللاجئين في الأردن
Place	Jordan
Year	2022 (submitted)
Type	Article
Title of Journal	Jordan Journal of Applied Science (JJOAS)
Frequency	Quarterly
Publisher	Applied Science Private University
ISBN/ISSN	Online: 2708-9126
Language	Arabic

Abstract

الملخص: هدفت الدراسة إلى فحص مدى فاعلية برنامج مستند للدعم النفسي الاجتماعي في رفع مستوى التمكين الأسري لدى اللاجئين في الأردن. وتكونت عينة الدراسة من (32) لاجئاً في محافظة إربد تم تعيينهم بشكل عشوائي لمجموعتين متساويتين: المجموعة التجريبية (ن=16) التي شاركت في برنامج الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي، والمجموعة الضابطة (ن=16) التي لم تشارك في أي برنامج تدخل. ولتحقيق أهداف الدراسة تم تطوير مقياس التمكين الأسري لجمع بيانات الدراسة في الاختبارات القبلية والبعدي لمجموعتي الدراسة، وفي الاختبار التبعي مع أفراد المجموعة التجريبية فقط، وبرنامج الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي. أظهرت نتائج الدراسة وجود فروق دالة إحصائية بين المجموعتين التجريبية والضابطة في متوسطات الدرجات على مقياس التمكين الأسري في الاختبار البعدي لصالح المجموعة التجريبية، وعدم وجود فروق دالة إحصائية بين متوسطات القياسين البعدي والتبعي في مقياس التمكين الأسري، مما يعكس ثبات تأثير البرنامج.

The study aimed to examine the effectiveness of a document program for psychosocial support in raising the level of family empowerment among refugees in Jordan. The study sample consisted of (32) refugees in Irbid governorate who were randomly assigned to two equal groups: the experimental group (n = 16) that participated in the psychosocial support program, and the control group (n = 16) that did not participate in any intervention program. To achieve the objectives of the study, the Family Empowerment assessment was developed to collect study data in the pre and post tests for the two study groups, and in the follow-up test with members of the experimental group only, and the psychosocial support program. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the mean scores on the family empowerment assessment in the post test in favor of the experimental group, and there were no statistically

significant differences between the means of the post and follow-up measures in the family empowerment scale, which reflects the stability of the program's impact.

The Effectiveness of a Training Program Based on Health Education to Improve Health Empowerment Level among Refugees in Jordan

Partner(s)	Yarmouk University
Author(s)	Ahmad Al-Shraifin, Faculty of Education, Yarmouk University Mu'ayyad Megdadi, Faculty of Education, Yarmouk University Amani Shatnawi, Faculty of information Technology and Computer science, Yarmouk University Anas ALSobeh, Faculty of information Technology and Computer science, Yarmouk University Aya Akkawi, Faculty of Art, Yarmouk University
Place	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences
Year	2022 (Accepted)
Type	Article
Title of Journal	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences
Frequency	Quarterly
Publisher	University of Jordan
ISBN/ISSN	Online ISSN 2663-6190 Print ISSN 1026-3721
Language	Arabic and English
Keywords	refugees, health education, health empowerment

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of a training program based on health education to improve the level of health empowerment among refugees in Jordan. The study sample consisted of (38) refugees in Irbid governorate, and they were randomly divided into two groups: the experimental group (n = 19) refugees (the group which received the training program) and the control group (n = 19) refugees (without any training intervention). To achieve the study objectives, the Health Empowerment Scale (HES) was adapted and used to

collect the study data in the pre- and post- tests for the two study groups and to carry out the follow-up tests for the members of the experimental group only as well as to the health education training program (Serrani Azcurra DJL., Elders Health Empowerment Scale. Spanish adaptation and psychometric analysis). The results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups and the differences are in favour of the experimental group. The results showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the average performance of the experimental group on (HES) in the post-test, and their average scores on the same scale on the follow-up test, which reflects the stability of the program's impact.

The Effectiveness of a Psychosocial Support-Based Program in Raising Legal Empowerment among Refugees in Jordan

Partner(s)	Yarmouk University
Author(s)	Ahmed Al-Sharifin, College of Education, Yarmouk University Nour Bahr, College of Education, Yarmouk University Amani "Moh'd Jumaa" Amin Shatnawi, Faculty of Information Technology and Computer Science, Yarmouk University Anas "Mohamed Ramadan" ALSobeh, Faculty of Information Technology and Computer Science, Yarmouk University
Title	فاعلية برنامج يستند إلى الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي في رفع مستوى التمكين القانوني لدى اللاجئين في الأردن
Place	National and International
Year	Submitted in 2022
Title of Journal	Dirasat: Human and Social Sciences
Publisher	University of Jordan
ISBN/ISSN	Online ISSN 2663-6190 Print ISSN 1026-3721
Language	Arabic and English
Keywords	Refugees, Psychosocial Support, Legal Empowerment. اللاجئين، الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي، التمكين القانوني
Abstract	
Abstract: The study aimed to examine the effectiveness of a psychosocial support program in raising the level of legal empowerment among refugees in Jordan. The study sample consisted of (38) refugees in Irbid governorate,	

and they were randomly assigned to two equal groups: the experimental group (n = 19) and participated in the psychosocial support program, and the control group (n = 19) that did not participate in any intervention program. To achieve the objectives of the study, the Legal Empowerment Scale was used. To collect study data in the pre and post tests for the two study groups, and in the follow-up test with members of the experimental group only, in addition to the psychosocial support program. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the mean scores on the legal empowerment scale in the post-test in favor of the experimental group, and the results showed that there were statistically significant differences between the means of the post and follow-up measurements, in the legal empowerment scale, which reflects the continuing impact of the program in improving legal empowerment.

The Effectiveness of a counselling program based on psychosocial support in raising the level of economic empowerment of Syrian refugees

Partner(s)	Yarmouk University
Author(s)	Ahmed Al-Sharifin, College of Education, Yarmouk University Nour Bahr, College of Education, Yarmouk University Amani "Moh'd Jumaa" Amin Shatnawi, Faculty of Information Technology and Computer Science, Yarmouk University Anas "Mohamed Ramadan" ALSobeh, Faculty of Information Technology and Computer Science, Yarmouk University
Title	فاعلية برنامج ارشادي يستند إلى الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي في رفع مستوى التمكين الاقتصادي لدى اللاجئين السوريين
Place	National and International
Year	Submitted
Type	Open Access
Title of Journal	المجلة الاردنية للعلوم التربوية Jordan Journal of Educational Sciences
Publisher	Yarmouk University
ISBN/ISSN	2303-9574
Language	Arabic and English
Keywords	اللاجئين، الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي، التمكين الاقتصادي.
Abstract	

الملخص: هدفت الدراسة إلى فحص مدى فاعلية برنامج مستند للدعم النفسي الاجتماعي في رفع مستوى التمكين الاقتصادي لدى اللاجئين في الأردن. تكونت عينة الدراسة من (38) لاجئًا في محافظة إربد، تم تعيينهم بشكل عشوائي لمجموعتين متساويتين: المجموعة التجريبية (ن=19) وشاركت في برنامج الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي، والمجموعة الضابطة (ن=19) التي لم تشارك في أي برنامج تدخل. لتحقيق أهداف الدراسة تم تطوير مقياس التمكين الاقتصادي؛ لجمع بيانات الدراسة في الاختبارات القبليّة والبعدية لمجموعتي الدراسة، وفي الاختبار التتبعي مع أفراد المجموعة التجريبية فقط، بالإضافة إلى برنامج الدعم النفسي الاجتماعي. أظهرت نتائج الدراسة وجود فروق دالة إحصائيًا بين المجموعتين التجريبية والضابطة في متوسطات الدرجات على مقياس التمكين الاقتصادي في الاختبار البعدي لصالح المجموعة التجريبية، وأظهرت النتائج عدم وجود فروق دالة إحصائيًا بين متوسطات القياسين البعدي والتتبعي، في مقياس التمكين الاقتصادي، مما يعكس ثبات تأثير البرنامج.

The study aimed to examine the effectiveness of a document program for psychosocial support in raising the level of economic development of refugees in Jordan. The study sample consisted of (38) refugees in Irbid governorate, who were randomly assigned to two equal groups: the experimental group (n = 19) and participated in the psychosocial support program, and the control group (n = 19) that did not participate in any intervention program. To achieve the objectives of the study, the economic measurement was built; To collect study data in the pre and post tests for the two study groups, and in the follow-up test with members of the experimental group only, in addition to the psychosocial support program. The results of the study showed that there were statistically significant differences between the experimental and control groups in the average scores on the economic development measurement in the post-test in favour of the experimental group, and the results showed that there were no statistically significant differences between the means of the post and follow-up measurements, in the economic development measurement , which reflects the stability of the program's impact.

3 Books

Fragments of Exile

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Tamara Bueno-Doral http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2954-1519 Maria Lara Alfonso Palazón Francisca Domínguez
Place	Madrid
Year	2022, in press, accepted
Type	Book
Title	Fragments of Exile, a selection of the Reflections (Espejismos) Photo, Poetry and Short Story awards
Publisher	Fragua (SPI Q1)
Language	Spanish
Keywords	Refugees, Transmedia, Representations, Exile, Testimonies, Art

Abstract

Introducción

Diariamente las noticias nos recuerden la dura realidad en la que viven 1 de cada 95 personas en el mundo, pero que, desde la comodidad de nuestra rutina, tendemos a olvidar: la situación de los refugiados. En el mejor de los casos, las imágenes del televisor nos muestran a una voluntaria de la Cruz Roja abrazando a un hombre desconsolado que acaba de pisar tierra firme tras un tormentoso viaje. En el peor, vemos el pequeño cuerpo sin vida de un niño de tres años siendo arrastrado hacia la costa por las olas.

La cifra de desplazados forzosos crece cada año. La pandemia que azotó al mundo a principios del 2020 y la invasión de Ucrania (que al momento de editar este libro aún continúa) no han hecho más que empeorar la situación. El número total de desplazados y refugiados sigue en aumento en el mundo y ya ha superado los 84 millones, según el último informe publicado por el Alto Comisionado de las Naciones Unidas para los Refugiados (Acnur, 2021)

Este aumento, sin embargo, lejos de generar una mayor comprensión entre la población, pareciera crecer en paralelo al surgimiento de discursos racistas y contra la inmigración, promovidos por grandes grupos sociales y políticos. Éstos intentan reforzar continuamente los aspectos negativos de la llegada de refugiados al país, asociándolos a la falta de trabajo, al incremento de la delincuencia y al mayor gasto público, formando en el

imaginario nacional estereotipos negativos que potencian la discriminación, poniendo el foco en las diferencias raciales, culturales, religiosas, étnicas, etc.

Así, en muchas ocasiones, tras el lacerante y peligroso trayecto que los refugiados llevan a cabo para escapar de conflictos, guerras, pobreza, violencia y abusos, el recibimiento que éstos tienen por parte de los países de acogida es casi tan desesperanzador e inhumano como el viaje mismo.

En la presente obra hemos querido recoger diversas miradas sobre el refugio y el exilio, fruto del llamamiento en forma de concurso que hicimos para recibir imágenes, poemas y relatos cortos que abordaran esta problemática. Esperamos que su lectura sea enriquecedora para todos aquéllos a los que les interese acercarse a esta realidad social que, lejos de desaparecer, va a seguir en aumento planteándonos preguntas esenciales para nuestro futuro como humanidad: ¿podemos vivir aislados en un mundo interconectado?, ¿nos puede ir bien a unos pocos si grandes capas de la población viven en condiciones inhumanas?, ¿podemos ser indiferentes al dolor y al sufrimiento de los demás y que esto no tenga consecuencias en nuestra propia vida?

Las editoras

El libro Espejismos: fragmentos de un exilio, se enmarca en las acciones divulgativas del proyecto de investigación RAISD (H2020 822688).

TEXTO CONTRAPORTADA

El número de seres humanos que huyen de sus países debido a la persecución, situaciones de conflicto o violaciones de los Derechos Humanos no ha dejado de aumentar en los últimos años. La cifra de desplazados forzados superó en 2020 el umbral de los 82,4 millones de personas, según datos de ACNUR, y seguirá creciendo de acuerdo con todas las previsiones. Sin embargo, esta grave emergencia humanitaria no está encontrando una respuesta digna por parte de los países de “acogida”. Contrariamente a lo dispuesto en la Convención de Ginebra, se están rechazando numerosas solicitudes de asilo de forma injustificada. Paralelamente, se incrementan los discursos racistas y contra la inmigración en las poblaciones, fomentados por algunos partidos políticos.

La presente obra nace de un llamamiento en forma de concurso en el que solicitábamos recibir poemas, imágenes y relatos cortos que aportaran diversas miradas sobre esta realidad. Esperamos que, gracias a observar dicha problemática social desde múltiples puntos de vista, los lectores puedan humanizar los fríos datos que se ofrecen sobre los refugiados, aumentando su comprensión sobre el tema al poder unir los distintos fragmentos de lo que significa la experiencia del exilio.

Educational innovation practices facing current challenges of the university: service learning, creativity and approaching professional reality

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Tamara Bueno-Doral http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2954-1519 ; María Lara https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6414-8034 Noelia García Castillo https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5875-0195
Title	Prácticas de innovación docente ante los desafíos actuales de la Universidad: Aprendizaje Servicio, desarrollo de la creatividad y acercamiento de la realidad profesional de la comunicación
Place	Madrid
Year	2022, in press (accepted)
Type	Book chapter
Title	Más allá de la didáctica tradicional (Beyond traditional teaching)
Number, date	6-7/10/2021
Publisher	Thompson Reuters
ISBN/ISSN	ISBN 978-84-1124-266-0
Language	Spanish
Keywords	Innovación docente – Aprendizaje servicio – Empleabilidad – Creatividad – Educación en valores
Abstract	
<p>Desde la crisis económica y social de 2008, se viene observando entre los universitarios una falta de motivación y de esperanza ante su futuro profesional. Ello se debe en parte al creciente paro juvenil y a la dificultad para realizar prácticas reales o entrar en relación con profesionales del sector de la Comunicación. Actualmente, a ello se le une la situación de inestabilidad sobrevenida de la pandemia, que ha suscitado numerosos análisis docentes de distintos países (como Daniels et al., 2021; Herold y Chen, 2021; Senn y Wessner, 2021; o Wildman et al., 2021).</p> <p>Durante el curso 2020-21, las autoras han desarrollado dos líneas de innovación docente para favorecer la motivación del alumnado de la Facultad de Ciencias de la Información, su profesionalización y su aprendizaje mediante la expresión artística y creativa:</p>	

- Actividades que fomentan la creatividad artística entre los alumnos de grado y encuentros con profesionales en activo.
- Proyectos de aprendizaje servicio (ApS) con alumnos de grado y máster en colaboración con 7 entidades no lucrativas y organizaciones culturales.

Estas experiencias docentes incorporan el punto de vista y las dinámicas del sector profesional a la formación, acercando a los estudiantes a las prácticas y conocimientos reales propios de la misma, favoreciendo así su posterior inserción laboral. A su vez, fomentan su creatividad y espíritu crítico indagando en su imaginario artístico y descubriendo sus mejores cualidades para poder expresarse profesional y emocionalmente en un contexto creativo (Dewey, 2008). Por último, estas actividades tienen un impacto social, trabajando directamente con algunos de los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible (ODS) y promoviendo en el alumnado valores propios de la emergente disciplina de la Investigación e Innovación Responsable (RRI). Entre ellos, el compromiso ético, la diversidad cultural, la inclusión de colectivos vulnerables, la igualdad de género y el diálogo entre los distintos actores sociales para dar respuesta a problemas complejos de la sociedad actual.

Los ejemplos aquí descritos no son casos aislados, sino que se enmarcan en los 20 años de aplicación del método docente de Proyecto Social Real y, algunas de las iniciativas, se desarrollan también en colaboración con el proyecto europeo Horizonte 2020 “Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced” (RAISD, identificador 822688).

4 Conference Proceedings

Educational innovation in European projects: Delving into forced migrations via organizing an international workshop

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Sara Parra Ferreras Thais Costa da Silva Liisa Hänninen http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8567-4201
Place	Madrid
Year	2022, in press, Accepted
Type	Conference and book chapter
Title	CUICIID 2021 Conference
Number, date	6-7/10/2021
Publisher	Thompson Reuters
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6783904
Language	English
Keywords	Educational innovation, RAISD project, forced migration, international workshop, Research for Change
Abstract	
<p>The new teaching innovation formulas can contribute to the great challenges of humanity, as is the case of the Real Social Project Method, which promotes learning through collaborative and supportive research and communication initiatives, embracing the principles of RRI, research and responsible innovation. Through the case study methodology and participant observation, an educational innovation initiative related to forced displacement is presented, carried out within the framework of a European project H2020 RAISD, focused on identifying vulnerable audiences among displaced migrants, exploring their needs and find suitable solutions. In spring 2021, three postgraduate researchers and a doctoral researcher, collaborators of the RAISD project, designed and organized an international youth congress around the theme: forced migration, gender and vulnerabilities. Trusting in the competence of young researchers, the Research for Change Workshop wanted to give prominence to undergraduate, master's and doctoral students, with the aim of providing them with a platform to present their work and improve their career in a creative and dynamic way. The event had a wide international impact, especially on social networks and through the ECRE platform, reaching 13,000 people.</p>	

This article describes the organization process, dissemination and results of Research for Change, from the prior strategic planning and design of the event to its subsequent celebration and evaluation. The event brought together nearly 40 researchers from 5 continents in 6 thematic tables for two days. The results were very positive, both from the perspective of the KPIs, and from a qualitative evaluation of the opinions of the participants. Likewise, a discussion is offered on the adequacy of the methodology for this type of activity.

Selective education experiences with highly vulnerable groups. Pilot experience in Palermo, Italy

Partner(s)	CESIE, Italy
Author(s)	L. Ardizzone , G. Barbieri , J. Mazaj
Title	ALL YOU CAN LEARN: increasing learners' decision-making capacity through selective education experiences with highly vulnerable groups among the forcibly displaced. Pilot experience in Palermo, Italy
Place	Spain
Year	Publication year: 2021
Type	Conference Proceedings Pages: 2699-2708
Conference	ICERI2021: 14th annual International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation
Number, date	ICERI2021 Proceedings
Relevant pages	2699-2708
Publisher	IATED
DOI	10.21125/iceri.2021.0684 10.5281/zenodo.6684091
ISBN/ISSN	ISBN: 978-84-09-34549-6 ISSN: 2340-1095
Language	English
Keywords	forced migration , forcibly displaced people , highly vulnerable groups , innovation in education , selective-education , responsible research and innovation .
Link(s)	https://library.iated.org/view/ARDIZZONE2021ALL
Abstract	

This work introduces a milestone of the project “RAISD: Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced” [Horizon 2020, grant 822688] aiming at identifying the most Vulnerable Groups among Forcibly Displaced People (FDP) in the EU influence area, analyse their specific needs and find suitable attention and inclusion practices to address them in variety of vulnerability contexts. Activated by urgencies rather than events, educational inclusion solutions are frequently reactive, partial and disregard some groups. In Italy, this reflects in a high number of NEET (Not in Education, Employment or Training) among FDP, consistent training dropout rates and lower female participation [1].

As there is still a tendency for national educational change policymakers and planners to ignore human factors [3], training providers too often assume to know and understand FDPs’ learning needs by default, thrusting learners into one-size-fits-all solutions while ignoring those individual factors and circumstances (pre-migration, in-transit, at-arrival) that strongly affect educational achievements.

The evidence for a need in ‘Change Management in Education Delivery Approaches’ that could focus on local/regional manifestations of global challenges and on ‘local’ opportunities for solving them [5], was suggested by the RAISD fieldwork findings under the action-research approach [6]:

(a) FDP interviews [13 Female (age 19 – 28): Nigeria, Gambia, Ghana; 12 Male (age 18 – 33): Gambia, Senegal, Ivory Coast and Guinea Conakry].

(b) local Quintuple Helix Stakeholder consultations (in total 11), to comply with activities of a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) architecture process [8].

The design of the novelty selective-learning training opportunity ‘ALL you can LEARN’ (allyoucanlearn.cesie.org, 2020) also adopts the four fundamental RRI characteristics: anticipation, reflection, inclusion, responsiveness [5], by introducing a more bottom-up and participatory practice to education, shifting from an “induced” training offer approach (i.e. a dominating and top-down way to organise education for FDPs and leave them either accepting or rejecting the contents of education) to a “selective” approach in developing a training offer in which several optional modules are offered and participants can choose contents that are attractive for them.

The ultimate aim is to increase learners’ decision-making capacity (in this specific case, Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions) as they are to be intended as “co-experts” of the RRI based inclusion strategy, thus having the opportunity to decide and co-design their personal learning experience according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.).

Thus, the work discusses how individual human factors and circumstances for vulnerability influence the effectiveness of training with FDP; describes the selective-approach methodological assets, the conceptualisation

process of learning objectives and final results of the piloting experiences with FDP women currently living in Sicily, during the 2021 c-19 pandemic, originally from Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Comoros and Tunisia.

Deconstruction of narratives and identification of hate speech

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Liisa Hänninen http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8567-4201
Title	Deconstrucción de narrativas e identificación de discursos de odio (sesión 2.2)
Place	Madrid
Year	2020
Type	Conference
Title	Refugees in the Academy (Aulas Refugio), conference for Complutense University lecturers about forced migration and refugees. UNHCR and Complutense shared activity.
Number, date	17-19/2/2020
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6786520
Language	Spanish
Keywords	Discriminative discourse, hate speech, migrants, refugees, incitation to violence
Link(s)	http://cfp.ucm.es/formacionprofesorado/aulas-refugio-en-la-academia
Abstract	
<p>In the current European societies, discriminative and hate discourse (hate speech) around the theme of migrants and refugees is becoming growingly popular. Research has shown that hate speech has considerable effects in the image and acceptance of migrants and can foster violent acts. The present communication focuses on how to identify, classify and deconstruct diverse expressions of hate speech. Research methods and practices are explained from a theory perspective and practical examples are also provided.</p>	

Webdoc Reflections/Webdoc Espejismos

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Tamara Bueno-Doral http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2954-1519 ; Alfonso Palazón María Lara https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6414-8034 Francisca Domínguez
Place	Granada
Year	2021
Type	Conference
Title	International Seminar on Transmedia and Crowdsourcing in Contemporary Mediatic Culture (Seminario Internacional Transmedialización y Crowdsourcing en la Cultura Mediática Contemporánea)
Number, date	16-17/6/2021
Language	Spanish
Keywords	Transmedia, Documentary, Refugees, Webdoc
Link(s)	https://www.nar-trans.com/evento/seminario-transmedializacion-programa/

Abstract

Captar la atención de los públicos en un entorno donde cada día surgen nuevas tecnologías, plataformas y contenidos no es tarea fácil. La multiplicidad de formas y canales para comunicar, y el nuevo rol del *prosumidor*, que no solo recibe la información sino que la co-crea junto con la marca, están generando nuevos desafíos en el ámbito de la comunicación. Pero este contexto no es necesariamente negativo: enfocado de la forma correcta, puede generar una mayor cercanía con el público, promover la participación activa y aportar mayor prestigio a las organizaciones y marcas.

En la presente comunicación nos centramos en el concepto de narrativa transmedia, definida por Scolari (2013) como “un tipo de relato donde la historia se despliega a través de múltiples medios y plataformas de comunicación, y en el cual una parte de los consumidores asume un rol activo en ese proceso de expansión”. Los objetivos específicos de nuestro paper son los siguientes: en primer lugar, exponer un exhaustivo estado de la cuestión sobre el transmedia en España, en segundo lugar, analizar los casos transmedia que han tenido un mayor éxito en los últimos años, detectando cuáles son las oportunidades y desafíos actuales, y por último, mostrar el diseño y principales acciones de un caso real, el proyecto transmedia *Espejismos*.

La muestra para el análisis de casos está compuesta por las campañas ganadoras en el Festival Iberoamericano de la Comunicación Publicitaria El Sol de 2019 en la categoría Campaña Integrada. Hemos seleccionado este año

debido a que, por la llegada de la pandemia del Covid-19, muchos de los festivales y certámenes publicitarios de 2020 fueron aplazados para 2021.

En cuanto a la finalidad y contenidos del proyecto webdoc *Espejismos*, buscamos comunicar la situación de los refugiados que llegan a España y las dificultades que experimentan los grupos más vulnerables en su lucha por sobrevivir e integrarse en la sociedad. De esta forma, mostramos el viaje después del viaje, mediante una compilación de las historias de desplazados forzados, que son visibilizadas a través de la campaña transmedia. La temática de los refugiados es multidimensional y el webdoc *Espejismos* busca reflejar esta realidad a través de una comunicación transmedia que explora las diferentes tecnologías y plataformas disponibles para visibilizar a los desplazados. Las distintas historias contadas en primera persona por los refugiados son también completadas por investigadores expertos en la materia tanto en el cortometraje documental, como en los materiales complementarios que nutren el webdoc. Asimismo, se expande el relato y enriquece el proyecto a través de una serie de medios y acciones que extienden el material rodado y que buscan una mayor involucración e interacción con el público.

El webdoc es el centro gravitatorio de estos contenidos, que están alojados en cinco secciones denominadas *Reflejos, Espejos, Ilusiones, Imágenes y Horizontes*, en las que se encuentran:

- Información relativa al webdoc, detalles sobre el proyecto RAISD, datos y cifras sobre refugiados.
- Material audiovisual (el cortometraje, entrevistas, piezas, podcast...).
- Relatos, poemas y fotografías derivadas de un concurso y publicadas en un libro asociado al webdoc.
- Galería o exposición de imágenes recopiladas a lo largo del proyecto.
- Otras iniciativas como las redes sociales de *Espejismos* (Instagram y Facebook), las acciones coordinadas entre refugiados y sus comunidades de acogida (que se organizan para generar una mayor integración de éstos en el tejido social), información sobre una aplicación para móviles que están desarrollando alumnos de la Universidad Complutense para dar apoyo a los estudiantes refugiados y un podcast que gira en torno a las historias de los especialmente vulnerables entre los desplazados forzosos.

Este enfoque multiplataforma y multiformato pretende acercar al público a la actual crisis de refugiados desde una perspectiva más directa, requiriendo no sólo de una mayor interacción por parte del usuario para acceder a todo el contenido disponible, sino que también permitiendo la co-creación en algunas de sus acciones.

Por último, señalamos que el webdoc *Espejismos* se enmarca en el proyecto internacional RAISD (*Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced* o *Mejora de las estrategias de atención e inclusión para personas especialmente vulnerables entre los desplazados forzados*), financiado por el programa de investigación e innovación de la Unión Europea *Horizon 2020* y formado por ocho socios (Universidades y ONGs) en siete países (España, Italia, Finlandia, Hungría, Turquía, Jordania y Líbano).

Participatory cinema and migration

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	María Lara, Tamara Bueno, Alfonso Palazón
Place	Lisbon, Portugal
Year	2022
Type	Conference
Title	ECREA Film Studies Section conference Film, Migration and the Archive
Number, date	June 2-3, 2022
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6860827
Language	English
Keywords	Refugees, Documentary, Transmedia, Co-production

Abstract

Based on a participatory methodological approach that triangulates Responsible Research and Innovation (Deblonde, 2015), action-research (Stringer, 2013) and socio-ecological models (Partelow, 2016), our research project on refugees has worked in action-research units located in 7 countries that make up the X European Project consortium (Finland, Italy, Turkey, Jordan, Hungary, Spain, and Lebanon). One of the most relevant results of the project has been the development of the documentary “Espejismos”. These units are permanent action-research laboratories in which all research and innovation actions have been co-designed with the rest of the involved social actors: NGO representatives, policy makers, researchers, businesses, refugees and asylum seekers, and other members of civil society related to this issue. In the case of Spain, where representatives from all these areas regularly participate, around twenty people have collaborated on the documentary and the transmedia webdoc, mainly refugees and asylum seekers, specialized researchers, and NGOs.

In this communication we present the most outstanding results of this participatory method in which the process of creation and production of the documentary has been supported, as well as the main findings regarding the challenges and synergies that have emerged throughout the process.

References:

- Deblonde, M. (2015). Responsible research and innovation: Building knowledge arenas for glocal sustainability research. *Journal of Responsible Innovation*, 2(1), 20-38.
- Partelow, S. (2016). Coevolving Ostrom’s social–ecological systems (SES) framework and sustainability science: four key co-benefits. *Sustainability Science*, 11(3), 399-410.
- Stringer, E. T. (2013). *Action research*. Sage publications.

Using collaborative methodology and communication for redefining and assessing new attention and inclusion strategies for forcible displaced people

Partner(s)	UCM Spain, CESIE Italy, UNIMED Italy
Author(s)	Liisa Hänninen, Luisa Ardizzone, Martina Zipoli
Place	Aarhus
Year	2022 (paper accepted)
Type	Conference
Title	ECREA 2022, 9 th European Communication Conference: Rethink impact
Number, date	19-22/10/2022
Publisher	ECREA
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6855666
Language	English
Keywords	Forcibly displaced people, attention and inclusion strategies, collaborative methodology, assessment, tailored strategies
Link(s)	https://conferences.au.dk/ecrea2022

Abstract

Finding suitable strategies for the inclusion of forcible displaced people is a challenge for the communities hosting migrants, especially in the current increasingly complex geopolitical, sanitary and climate crisis situation where armed conflicts, ethnical and religious discrimination, sexual harassment and political opinions, among other reasons, force millions of people to flee from their home countries and regions. Tailoring these strategies in the host countries is often complex and requires a correct analysis of the forced migrants' need, and an understanding of how the personal situation of each migrant is tangled with the above-mentioned conditions. Forced migration can only be understood taking into account the contexts (economic, social, legislative, political, personal) that make migrants vulnerable.

The current presentation describes how an international consortium formed by Mediterranean, Northern, Central European and Middle Eastern countries worked together with forcibly displaced people, aid organizations and other relevant stakeholders in studying, designing and evaluating 8 pilots of tailored attention and inclusion strategies for forcibly displaced people, known with the acronym of TAIS. In the first phase of the project, an extensive field study with more than 178 interviews to forcibly displaced persons was carried out in Spain, Italy, Finland, Hungary, Turkey, Jordan and Lebanon, contributing to the knowledge of forced migrants' particular difficulties, vulnerability contexts and needs in the participating countries.

Afterwards, the intensive co-creation work of the so called 'Action Research Units' in the 7 participating countries – formed by academics, experts, refugees, NGOs, policy makers, researchers and even some representatives from the business world – resulted in 8 pilot strategies for inclusion. Altogether, more than 100 workshops and meetings were held in 7 countries along the 3 years project, including 3 international cross-analysis workshops where the process and results of the integration strategies were shared and assessed. Inclusive and transparent communication was a key success driver for informing about and executing these pilot experiences, and putting together the inputs and efforts of more than 320 stakeholders. Refugee aid organizations got highly engaged in the project and contributed with their first-hand field experience and strategic proficiency to all the phases of the project.

The focus of the paper is describing the integration strategies and the communication efforts related to them, as well as sharing the methodology and results of an innovative and inclusive evaluation system of the outcomes. The extent to which these tailored strategies will be adapted and replicated in similar vulnerable contexts remains an open question, but still, several NGOs and humanitarian agencies, as well as organisations working on a daily basis with local communities, have showed their interest in the working methodology. The continuity of the project action is also envisioned, and a new observatory on forced migration will be presented to the conference participants.

Integrating forced migrants in the research and communication project using the principles of Responsible Research and Innovation.

Partner(s)	Anadolou University, Turkey Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Tayfun Dalkilic Noelia García Castillo Maria Lara
Place	Aarhus
Year	2022 (paper accepted)
Type	Conference
Title	ECREA 2022, 9 th European Communication Conference: Rethink impact
Number, date	19-22/10/2022
Publisher	ECREA
Doi	10.5281/zenodo.6860996
Language	English
Keywords	Forced migrants, RRI, open participation, migration research, communication
Link(s)	https://conferences.au.dk/ecrea2022

Abstract

The application of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) to migration studies and communication represents a clear interpretative and methodological advantage. RRI provides a more holistic vision for the understanding of the phenomenon and focuses on a co-design 'with and for' the migrants and 'with and in' the society.

Furthermore, RRI emphasizes the inclusiveness, open participation, transparency, and responsive change with local responses to address global challenges. To that end the concept of 'quintuple helix', one of the principles of RRI, is essential. This is to include in the whole research, innovation and communication process the stakeholders who represent the different social actors, including civil society (NGOs and citizens, considering forced migrants themselves), academy and education (e.g., universities and research centers), policy makers (local and national, related with migration and refugee policy), and business world. Following the quintuple helix, 7 action-research units (ARUs) have been created in Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey, Hungary, Finland, Italy, and Spain to co-design different tailored attention and inclusion strategies (TAIS) for distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly

displaced. Due to that, with the application of RRI, migrants and forced migrants can become the focus of the innovation and communication processes.

The participation in the project was limited to those people who felt psychologically benefited by their participation in the Project, following the protocols and considerations established by RAISD Ethics Plan previously approved by the European Commission.

Forced migrants in these 7 ARUs actively participated in the design and evaluation of the TAISs. In addition, some forced migrants have been key providers of services for the implementation of certain tailored attention and inclusion strategies. Significant communication results have also been achieved thanks to the participation of 17 people belonging to diverse profiles among forced migrants in a documentary film and other transmedia items. The active participation of forced migrants enriches the experience of all stakeholders. As stated by a representative of an NGO collaborating with RAISD: 'A very important asset has been that in these spaces of joint work there has been something that is evident, but infrequent, which is the participation of the displaced people. Their experience at origin, on transit, on arrival, in the procedures, in the responses, in the reception... It is essential to be able to improve, redesign and establish strategies'.

However, the inclusion of vulnerable groups among forced migrants in all research, innovation and communication processes also poses several challenges. Even more with online activities due to the pandemic. Difficulties such as language, digital divide, the characteristics of the host society, migratory grief, educational level, or lack of self-assurance to collaborate on equal terms with the rest of stakeholders require prior training and careful preparation, so that their participation in the research project and its communication can be fully effective, significant, and diverse.

This compilation of advances, challenges and recommendations derived from the specific cases in these 7 countries are of great importance for the development and adaptation of future research and communication projects.

Rethinking vulnerabilities via intersectional approaches to migration contexts, intercultural and interpersonal communication

Partner(s)	Anadolou University, Turkey Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Nezih Orhon Tamara Bueno Doral Elif Akcakaya
Place	Aarhus
Year	2022 (paper accepted)
Type	Conference
Title	ECREA 2022, 9 th European Communication Conference: Rethink impact
Number, date	19-22/10/2022
Publisher	ECREA
Language	English
Keywords	Forced migrants, vulnerabilities, vulnerability context, intercultural communication, intersectional approaches
Link(s)	https://conferences.au.dk/ecrea2022

Abstract

Forced displacements create vulnerabilities and need to be understood as they primarily define migration and migration contexts. Forced migration, which is caused by many reasons such as humanitarian crises, political conflicts, discrimination, and violence, causes a variety of vulnerabilities to arise in various aspects. Although vulnerability creates effects at different social levels, it can be severely experienced at the individual level, and therefore vulnerability can be experienced as different as the number of individuals in a society. This indicates a subjective aspect of vulnerability. This subjectivity also depends on the fact that vulnerability is the result of a combination of the effects of different factors in a context. Therefore, intersectional approaches to migration contexts and interpersonal communication even become more crucial to understand those aspects of vulnerabilities in different levels and in different settings.

Vulnerability is a multi-dimensional, differential, scale-dependent and dynamic concept which in any context, has an accumulative nature. Vulnerabilities hit hardest to those individuals who have multiple exposing features. In addition to being sensitive to contextual factors, when studying vulnerabilities, one needs to recognize their

accumulative nature with an intersectional approach. This allows new findings and prevents making fixed hierarchies and, thus, essentializing the research subjects and their vulnerabilities.

Throughout 7 countries in the project, the essential aim as behalf of the intersectional approaches was to understand the different layers and patterns of "vulnerability contexts". Based on our approach so far, we were able to see vulnerability as a matrix of three main elements. The first is how the individual appears in the matrix. The second is the context, the different levels (micro, meso, and macro) of the individual's environment. The context is when and where the individual appears (in his/her complexity with all the characteristics mentioned earlier, condition, and coping mechanism) in the environment. The context may have a substantial impact on the first element. It may activate, deepens, provoke, prevent, mitigate and cease it. The third is the area where the individual perceives, consciously or subconsciously experiences the danger, damage, or vulnerability caused by the interconnected individual conditions and contexts. These main areas are the primary needs, fundamental human rights and identity. Also, the circumstances and dimensions that form the contexts for vulnerability do play a crucial role in intersectional approaches.

Factors such as age, gender, religion, culture, education, job opportunities and access to fundamental rights should be taken into consideration. In this context, the conditions of each individual (issues of interpersonal and intercultural communication) and the conditions (issues of context) are effective in defining vulnerability. Vulnerability emerges based on someone's personal condition in a given context, it is not an endowment or personal quality. It is a personal status that may result in vulnerability activated by the given context. Contexts are fluid elements, which requires analysis from the perspective of the actual person. For this reason, creating an operational definition of vulnerability context considering different aspects of communication allows a more flexible definition through intersectional approaches in 7 participating countries of the project.

Rethinking the impact of media discourse on migration and forced migration: the view of migrants and other stakeholders in Spain before and during the pandemic

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Noelia García Castillo Tamara Bueno Doral Liisa Hänninen
Place	Aarhus
Year	2022 (paper accepted)
Type	Conference
Title	ECREA 2022, 9 th European Communication Conference: Rethink impact
Number, date	19-22/10/2022
Publisher	ECREA
Language	English
Keywords	Forced migration, impact, media discourse, stakeholder view, pandemic
Link(s)	https://conferences.au.dk/ecrea2022

Abstract

Migration did not feature among the main media topics in Spain in 2020 because of the impact of Covid-19. However, 2021 has witnessed an upturn in media coverage of migration, coinciding with regional election campaigns and the Ceuta migrant crisis.

The application of Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) to media discourse on migration and forced migration represents a clear interpretative and methodological advantage, because RRI emphasizes the inclusiveness, open participation, transparency, and responsive change with local responses to address global challenges. Furthermore, with the application of RRI, migrants and forced migrants become the focus of the research and innovation process as well as of the media narrative.

In this communication, our main objectives are:

- To analyze the opinions of various stakeholders, both individuals and CSOs, regarding media discourse on migration and forced migration before and during the Covid-19.
- To compile and propose good practices to improve these narratives, and hence, their potential effect on the integration of migrants and forced migrants.

For this purpose, within the context of the RAISD project, we conducted 25 interviews in August - October 2019 with highly vulnerable, forcibly displaced people. We also administered an open-ended questionnaire to 16 representatives of national and international stakeholders who represent the quintuple helix of RRI (NGOs, migrants and refugees themselves, other members of civil society, policymakers, researchers, businesses, and representatives in the field of education), in spring 2021.

The information we collected has enabled us to present a wide range of perspectives from different stakeholders regarding the potential consequences of media discourse on migrants and forced migrants. In addition, we have compiled existing and novel proposals for good practices that may counteract biased communication and consequently give rise to new actions that could potentially be replicated in other regions.

Our results evidence a worsening of media discourse on migration in Spain with an increase in criminalization and politicization. Participants in the study reported that the media discourse affected them both personally and professionally, and that media discourse should explain the causes of forced and economic displacement avoiding the homogenization of migrant people. Thus, diverse testimonies presented by the migrants themselves would undoubtedly be helpful, respecting their anonymity where necessary.

Likewise, good practices to improve these narratives, and hence their potential effect on the integration of migrants, have also been compiled and proposed. These suggestions include new inclusive audiovisual and information projects, the incorporation of migrant or racialized journalists, and the development of codes of ethics and even legislative changes.

This proposal provides a necessary additional focus and framework, by means of a participatory and inclusive methodology, for interpreting research that explores media content through qualitative and quantitative analyses of journalistic discourse. This communication promotes the objective of 'researching with' rather than 'researching on' migrants and forced migrants so as not to perpetuate the invisibilization of migrants that is so widely criticized in academia whenever it is observed in media discourse.

Co-design of an Inclusive Training in Digital Skills with Refugee Women

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Tamara Bueno-Doral http://orcid.org/0000-0002-2954-1519 Noelia García Castillo https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5875-0195
Place	Madrid
Year	2022, paper accepted
Type	Conference
Title	CUICIID 2022
Number, date	6-8/10/2022
Language	Spanish
Keywords	Aprendizaje inclusivo; Refugiadas; Aprendizaje Servicio; Género; Habilidades digitales.
Link(s)	https://cuiciid.net/

Abstract

Las tecnologías de la comunicación y la alfabetización digital pueden suponer factores de exclusión en colectivos vulnerables que tienen más dificultades para realizar un aprendizaje autónomo, ya que no contar con estas habilidades dificulta su acceso a la formación y a la inserción laboral.

Mediante una práctica de inclusión social diseñada en base a metodologías participativas, como la Investigación e Innovación Responsables o la Investigación-Acción, un equipo transdisciplinar de investigadores/as, profesores/as, migrantes, estudiantes, miembros de ONGs y de empresas especializadas ha ofrecido a un grupo de mujeres refugiadas en situación de especial vulnerabilidad un programa formativo que, dirigido al emprendimiento y a la inserción laboral, fomentaba la adquisición de habilidades digitales. Para el diseño inicial de la práctica de inclusión social que se presenta en esta comunicación se trabajó en dos talleres de una jornada de duración cada uno, detectando el grupo vulnerable con el que trabajar y co-diseñando el programa de formación en base a la información del trabajo de campo que todos estos actores proporcionaron, incluyendo por supuesto al propio colectivo de personas refugiadas.

Asimismo, se presenta y analiza una experiencia de Aprendizaje Servicio con alumnado universitario que ha favorecido la inclusión social de las mujeres refugiadas en la universidad y la formación real de este alumnado de la educación reglada.

Los objetivos específicos han sido los siguientes:

- Proporcionar al colectivo los conocimientos y habilidades digitales necesarios para su inclusión laboral.

- Trabajar con el colectivo diversas capacidades digitales necesarias para su inclusión social en las comunidades de acogida.
- Entrenar al colectivo en el uso de las tecnologías de la comunicación que pueden favorecer proyectos de emprendimiento.
- Favorecer la inclusión social del colectivo en la universidad mediante experiencias de innovación docente desarrolladas en colaboración con el alumnado de la educación reglada.

La presente comunicación es una propuesta metodológica para la formación ética e inclusiva de colectivos especialmente vulnerables que podría ser replicada por otras organizaciones. Además, supone una contribución al estado del arte actual, ya que las refugiadas constituyen un colectivo que suele estar representado de una forma pasiva en los estudios sobre migrantes y habilidades digitales. A su vez, mediante el Aprendizaje Servicio, se avanza por parte del alumnado universitario en el trabajo real y directo con mujeres refugiadas; así, ambas partes avanzan en la inclusión, en el conocimiento del otro y en la reducción de estereotipos en este contexto de cambio hacia un ecosistema cada vez más digital.

Embedding gender approach in international research: An example of a European project on forced migration

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Liisa Hänninen
Place	Madrid
Year	2022 (paper accepted)
Type	Conference
Title	CUICIID 2022
Number, date	6-8/10/2022
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6856349
Language	English
Keywords	Gender, intersectional approach, gender-responsive, forced migrants, EU research.
Link(s)	https://cuiciid.net/

Abstract

In real world social research settings with participatory focus, gender equality practice can represent huge challenges in terms of discrimination, contrary attitudes and long lived social norms, especially when it comes to research habits. If observed under an intersectional point of view and considering that the project focused on vulnerable collectives among the forcibly displaced people, the challenges double. Special requirements apply when researching highly vulnerable people and people in forced displacement. The current paper delves into the reality of a European H2020 project with the aim of exploring how diverse aspects of gender were transversally embedded into the research process in seven participating countries, including partner from Europe and Middle East. Though gender balance in research teams, work division and decision making have become a must in Horizon projects, and gender focus in all research stages recommendable, putting these aspects into practice proved to be highly challenging. The specific objective of the paper is to show how gender equity aspects were integrated into the project team, research practice and resulting innovation activities. Exploring if it would be possible to move from merely gender-aware and -sensitive practices to entirely gender-responsive and even gender-transformative approaches was also included in the study.

From the methodology perspective, the paper uses case study and participatory observation methods. It shows a practical case of embedding gender into a project -the research concept, structures and practice- in a highly culturally diverse and demanding research setting, with very specific initial gender requirements, included in the

project's Grant Agreement. It offers an inside vision of the project, the difficulties and benefits of reaching towards fully gender responsive responses in international settings and in the daily research practice.

The results show that initial training in gender and the related concept of Responsible Research and Innovation are required, and constant reminders about relative aspects are recommended. The integration of gender in the structures of the research environment and intersectional application during all the phases of the project are described, including partners' insights about how this task was accomplished. The level of integration was considered mostly gender-responsive, with a few advances towards the level of gender-transformative action. Finally, as a learning result from the project experience, a step to step guide to embedding gender in R&I is offered.

Frames of participation: Reception centre professionals' perceptions on asylum seekers' participation in Finland

Partner(s)	University of Helsinki, Finland
Author(s)	Martta Myllylä
Place	Online/ University of Oulu, Oulu, Finland
Year	2022
Type	Conference Presentation
Conference	Annual Sociology Days 2022: DEMOCRACY!
Date	24 th -25 th March 2022
Language	English

Abstract

Both asylum legislation and institutional practices of asylum seekers' reception system create barriers for asylum seekers' inclusion in European societies. In Finland, asylum seekers are excluded from integration training and comprehensive social and health care, their right to work is restricted and they are often placed in reception centres situated in remote areas with limited access to the surrounding society. Moreover, precarious status and protracted waiting periods decrease people's well-being and their capabilities for social and political participation. Despite severe marginality, many asylum seekers have surpassed the obstacles set in their way and participate in various spheres of society: they create social relations, enter the labour market and education, contribute to their local communities and engage in political activities. However, participation is not inherently emancipatory or voluntary, while asylum seekers are demanded certain kind of participation by the authorities and in the public and policy discourses.

In Finland, all asylum applicants are under the jurisdiction of one of the reception centres which are responsible for the provision of reception services including reception allowance, basic social and health services, study and work activities and interpretation services. Reception centre professionals are responsible for implementing the reception policies and thus have a crucial role in bordering and promoting asylum seekers' participation. In this paper, I examine, how reception centre professionals perceive asylum seekers' participation and professionals' own role in facilitating it. Drawing on a preliminary analysis of eight focus-group discussions with professionals (n=55) of the Finnish Red Cross reception centres, conducted in 2019, I present three frames of participation: participation as a duty, participation as rehabilitation, and participation as inclusion.

There are few appropriate services for families who are transferred to Finnish reception centres from the Greek Islands

Partner(s)	University of Helsinki, Finland
Author(s)	Antti Kivijärvi & Martta Myllylä
Title	Kreikan pakolaislertä saapuvia odottaa palvelutyhjiö. (Engl. Refugees arriving from Greek camps are faced by a lack of services)
Place	Finland
Year	2020
Type	Opinion piece
Title of Conference	Helsingin Sanomat
Date	28 th of May, 2020
Publisher	Sanoma Oy.
Language	Finnish
Link(s)	https://www.hs.fi/mielipide/art-2000006520789.html

Also men should have the right to flee from violence and persecution

Partner(s)	University of Helsinki, Finland
Author(s)	Antti Kivijärvi & Martta Myllylä
Title	Myös miehillä tulee olla oikeus paeta vainoa ja väkivaltaa (Engl. Also the men have the right to flee from persecution and violence)
Place	Finland
Year	2021
Type	A leading opinion piece in the most widely read newspaper in Finland (Helsingin Sanomat).
Title	Helsingin Sanomat
Date	8 th of September, 2021
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6786242
ISSN	0355-2047
Publisher	Sanoma Oy.
Language	Finnish
Link(s)	https://www.hs.fi/mielipide/art-2000008239917.html

Vulnerability Profiling and Dynamics of Monitoring as an Advocacy Approach: Case of RAISD Project

Partner(s)	Anadolu University, Turkey
Author(s)	Prof. Erol Nezir Orhon Prof. Dr. Deniz Kılıç Research Asist. Elif Akçakaya Research Asist. Tayfun Dalkılıç
Place	Turkey
Year	2021
Type	Conference booklet
Title	Conference

Relevant pages	95
Publisher	International Congress on Migration Researches (ICOMIR2021)
ISBN/ISSN	978-605-06728-7-9
Language	Turkish/English
Link(s)	https://www.icomir.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/01/icomir-ozet-kitabi-8.pdf

Abstract

The primary questions that come to mind in relation to vulnerable groups and approaches to vulnerability are "who are vulnerable", "what kind of issues or things they are vulnerable to", "why they are vulnerable for", "approaches to eliminating vulnerabilities" and "the impact of possible approaches on vulnerability". While seeking answers to these questions, it is aimed to describe both vulnerability and reveal the contexts related to vulnerability. In addition to all these fundamental approaches, vulnerability profiling and associated monitoring dynamics should also be seen as an advocacy issue, especially for groups displaced for different reasons to be a part of both diversity and inclusive approaches in the society they enter. In this direction, sharing the approaches and results of RAISD, which is the Horizon2020 project, can be seen as a fundamental benefit.

Addressing the challenge of forced displacement

Partner(s)	Anadolu University, Turkey
Author(s)	Prof. Dr. Erol Nezh Orhon Prof. Dr. Deniz Kılıç Research Asist. Duygu Keçeli Research Asist. Elif Akçakaya Research Asist. Tayfun Dalkılıç
Title	Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Place	Turkey
Year	2021
Type	Conference booklet
Title	International Medicine, Health and Communication Sciences Congress Booklet
Publisher	International Medicine, Health and Communication Sciences Congress
Language	English
Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations Inclusion strategy, vulnerable group, displaced people, vulnerability context, personalisation, community adapted, action research unit, methodology, data collection, data mining, collaborative software.

Abstract

RAISD, savaşlar ve krizler nedeniyle "Zorla Yerinden Edilmiş Kişiler" (FDP) arasında belirgin bir şekilde Korunmasız Grupların (VG'ler) dikkate alınması ve dahil edilmesi için etkili -iletişim ve dikkati çekeme- stratejilere duyulan ihtiyacı ele alır. Genel amacı, bu grupları, onların özel zorluklarını ve ihtiyaçlarını belirlemek, onlar için Uyarlanmış Dikkat ve Dahil Etme Stratejilerini (TAIS'ler) keşfedebilmek ve sağlayabilmektir.

VG'lerin göç durumlarının ayrıntılı açıklaması (VG'lerin göç durumlarının ayrıntılı sınıflandırması ve son derece hassas grupların profillemesi); yerinden edilmiş insanlar için fırsatlar ve zorluklar VG'lerin dahil edilmesiyle ilgili olarak topluluklara ev sahipliği yapmak için fırsatlar ve zorlukların tanımlanması; yerinden edilmiş kişilerin entegrasyonu için potansiyel ve direnç (ev sahibi topluluklarla ilgili olarak) noktalarının belirlenmesi; göçün sosyal sistemler üzerindeki etkileri; işgücü piyasalarına erişim ve bunlar üzerindeki etki; kurumsal (veya diğer araçların) dikkat ve katılım uygulamaları; kamu ve yerel katılım girişimleri ve ev sahibi topluluklar üzerindeki baskıyı hafifletmek için uygulamaların (uygun olmayan veya şiddetle tavsiye edilen) ve çözümlerin belirlenmesi gibi temel başlıkları ülke bağlamları açısından ele almayı amaçlamaktadır.

5 Grey literature (not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g. reports)

The following table reports all project Deliverables, available in Green Open Access at Zenodo and at the project website <https://raisd-h2020.eu/resources/scientific-outputs/>.

Deliverable	DOI	Author(s)	Year
RAISD D3.2 Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies: Methodology and Guidelines	10.5281/zenodo.6683728	Tamara Bueno Doral, Noelia García Castillo, & Liisa Hänninen	2020
RAISD D3.3 Research Methodology and Guidelines - preliminary version	10.5281/zenodo.6683706	Clara Guilló Girard; Tamara Bueno Doral; Rubén Fuentes Fernández; Noelia García Castillo; María Lara Martínez; Liisa Hänninen	2020
RAISD D3.4 TAIS Methodology and Guidelines	10.5281/zenodo.6683747	Liisa Hänninen, Noelia García Castillo, Rubén Fuentes-Fernández, Tamara Bueno Doral, Cristina Pérez, & Verónica Verdejo	2022
RAISD D3.5 Recommendations on the adoption of a TAIS-oriented approach	10.5281/zenodo.6683802	Luisa Ardizzone, Béla Soltész, Nezh Orhon, Noelia García Castillo, Martta Myllylä, Amani M. Shatnawi, & Anwar Kawtharani	2022
RAISD D4.1 Cross-Analysis: Vulnerability Context_Definition and Guidelines	10.5281/zenodo.6683823	Nezh Orhon; Tayfun Dalkılıç; Elif Akcakaya; All Partners	2021
RAISD D4.2 Synthesis Report about Vulnerability Profiling & Vulnerability Contexts	10.5281/zenodo.6683837	E. Nezh Orhon; Tayfun Dalkılıç; Elif Akcakaya; All Partners	2021
RAISD D4.3 Catalogue of Vulnerability Context	10.5281/zenodo.6683847	Mervi Pantti; Antti Kivijärvi	2021
RAISD D5.1 Catalogue of attention and inclusion practices for FDP in the EU influence area	10.5281/zenodo.6683855	Anwar Kawtharani; All Partners	2021
RAISD D5.2 TAIS: Definition and Guidelines - preliminary version	10.5281/zenodo.6683963	Béla Soltész; All Partners	2020

RAISD D5.3 TAIS: Definition and Guidelines	10.5281/zenodo.6683944	Béla Soltész; All Partners	2022
RAISD D5.4 Catalogue of TAIS for Vulnerable Groups	10.5281/zenodo.6683972	Martta Myllylä; All Partners	2022
RAISD D6.1 Training and evaluation materials	10.5281/zenodo.6684005	Emilia Stoduto; Raniero Chelli	2020
RAISD D6.2 Implementation of TAISs in ARUs	10.5281/zenodo.6684017	Raniero Chelli; Martina Zipoli; Emilia Stoduto; All Partners	2022
RAISD D6.3 Report on the involvement of local stakeholders	10.5281/zenodo.6698036	Raniero Chelli; Emilia Stoduto; Martina Zipoli; All Partners	2022
RAISD D7.1 Research stories from Action Research Units	10.5281/zenodo.6684022	Martina Zipoli; Emilia Stoduto; Raniero Chelli; All Partners	2021
RAISD D7.2 Cross-pilot workshop reports	10.5281/zenodo.6684026	Luisa Ardizzone; Jelena Mazaj	2022
RAISD D7.3 Actor-oriented and integrated evaluation	10.5281/zenodo.6684039	Antti Kivijärvi	2021
RAISD D7.4 TAIS EVALUATION CRITERIA: actor-oriented and integrated evaluation	10.5281/zenodo.6684045	Antti Kivijärvi	2022
RAISD D8.1 Requirements for the CRIOS	10.5281/zenodo.6684074	Anas M. Al-Sobeh; Amani M. Shatnawi; Mohammed Ghazi Al-Zame; Luisa Ardizzone; Alberto Provenzano; Rubén Fuentes-Fernández	2020
RAISD D8.2 CRIOS Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software Tool	10.5281/zenodo.6697939	Rubén Fuentes-Fernández; Anas M. Al-Sobeh; Amani M. Shatnawi; Fadi Yamout	2022
RAISD D9.8 Scientific and non-scientific (events, conferences and journals)	10.5281/zenodo.6884926	Luisa Ardizzone; Jelena Mazaj; All Partners	2022
RAISD D9.9 Policy Brief	10.5281/zenodo.6697771	Tamara Bueno-Doral; Rubén Fuentes-Fernández; Noelia García Castillo; All Partners	2022
RAISD D9.10 ESPEJIMOS Video Documentary	10.5281/zenodo.6697709	Alfonso Palazón Meseguer; Tamara Bueno Doral; María Lara Martínez	2022

RAISD D9.10 ESPEJIMOS Video Documentary	10.5281/zenodo.6697709	Alfonso Palazón Meseguer; Tamara Bueno Doral; María Lara Martínez	2022
---	------------------------	---	------

6 TAIS Specific publications

“ALL you can LEARN” (AUCL)

Partner(s)	CESIE
Author(s)	Luisa Ardizzone, Aday Lopez, Alberto Provenzano, Jelena Mazaj
Place	Palermo, Italy (online)
Year	2020
Type	Open Educational Resource
Language	Italian/English
Link(s)	https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/learn Written instructions on how to navigate the AUCL MENU https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/files/DASI-guide_learner_en.pdf Video instructions on how to navigate the AUCL MENU video tutorial.mkv https://youtu.be/tQxQwIPMsFI
Abstract	
<p>The bilingual online selection tool (Italian and English) represents the digital “learning menu” that supports the TAIS SELECTIVE approach: trainees choose their learning path; digital users can cross select between different areas of knowledge/challenges to be achieved during the overall “ALL you can LEARN” training experience. Through a group code, participants access the online tool and are approached ‘just’ as adult learners with no indication of names or titles to their vulnerabilities.</p>	

All you can LEARN

Adult education can play a key role for inclusive societies through its transformative possibilities and the power of the joy of learning.

Compose your Training Menu by choosing the learning objectives you want to achieve, distributed over 7 knowledge areas for inclusion: active citizenship and democracy – health and wellbeing – lifeskills – social cohesion, equity and equality – employment and work – digitalisation – inclusive societies and cultures.

All you can TEACH

Migration Teaching Resources for professionals in education to support skills development for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as in Higher Education.

Explore guidance, training and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of migration.

ALL you can LEARN

Compose your Training Menu by choosing the learning objectives you want to achieve, demonstrating that adult education can play a key role, through its transformative possibilities and the power of the joy of learning.

Login

Register

100 Learning Objectives to choose from, to:

- increase your decision-making capacity
- have direct influence over your individual learning path's content
- experience alternative learning and teaching methods depending on your personal interests, needs, wishes.
- protect the fulfilment of your fundamental rights by better understanding the Italian context and the available opportunities for inclusion.

All learning outcomes

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fdu.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

“ALL you can LEARN” Trainees’ Diary

Partner(s)	Palermo, Italy
Author(s)	CESIE
Title	(Training introduction; full display of learning objectives to select from their individual learning path; assessment tool after each chosen training session and study visit). Parallel text Italian-English.
Place	Palermo, Italy
Year	2020
Type	Printed Manual
Pages	101
	100 Printed hard copies for trainees, distributed also to mentors/trainers/stakeholders.
Link(s)	https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/files/all_you_can_learn-trainees_diary.pdf
Abstract	
<p>AUCL produced a gender-sensitive handout publications (Trainees’ Diary) and used gender-sensitive language and visual materials while teaching and writing course materials. A proof-reading in both language versions was done to ensure the used language avoids projecting stereotypical gender roles.</p> <p>The Trainee’s in-training Diary includes Self-assessment: Skill Analysis and Language proficiency; Daily training evaluation template; Daily observations with trainers and final dedicated session on evaluation and capitalisation). It features 100 Learning Objectives distributed over 7 knowledge areas for inclusion:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ active citizenship and democracy, ▪ health and wellbeing, ▪ life skills, ▪ social cohesion, ▪ equity and equality, ▪ employment and work, ▪ digitalisation, ▪ inclusive societies and cultures. 	

“ALL you can TEACH” Educational Resources for Professionals in the field of MIGRATION

Partner(s)	CESIE
Place	Palermo, Italy (online)
Year	2020
Type	Open Educational Resource
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.6845509
Link(s)	https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach https://cesie.org/en/higher-education-and-research/allyoucanlearn-training-experience/

Abstract

Migration Teaching Resources for professionals in education to support skills development for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as in Higher Education. Explore guidance, training and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of migration. The Community of Users can register to comment and rate all current 161 educational resources. Registered users can propose new material to be uploaded to the online database.

The screenshot shows the RAISD website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the title "Educational Resources for Professionals in the field of MIGRATION" and a "Want to do more?" button. Below the title, there is a welcome message and a description of the resource database. The main content area features three dropdown filters: "Type of Resource" (set to All), "Target groups" (set to All), and "Educational Challenge" (set to All). There is a search bar with the placeholder "Search by title..." and a "Search" button. Below the search bar, there is a "Sort By" dropdown menu set to "Title". At the bottom of the search area, there is a "Clear all filters" button and a message "Resources found: 161". A pagination bar at the bottom shows "Previous", "1", "2", "3", "4", "5", "9", and "Next".

Vulnerable refugees. Training exercises based on true stories

Partner(s)	Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants, Hungary
Author(s)	Bisztrai, Márton – Bognár, Katalin – László, Zsuzsa
Place	Budapest, Hungary
Year	2022
Type	Training handbook
Relevant pages	1-88
Publisher	<i>Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants</i>
Language	English and Hungarian
Keywords	social work, training, refugees
Link(s)	HU: https://tudastar.menedek.hu/hirek/raisd-munkafuzet EN: https://tudastar.menedek.hu/hirek/raisd-handbook

Abstract

“Vulnerable refugees. Training exercises based on true stories” is a practical handbook with refugee “profiles” and training exercises linked to them. Based on the empirical evidence collected by the RAISD project, Hungarian social workers present detailed “profiles” of refugees, based on anonymised summaries of real-life stories and life situations, and vulnerability contexts. These profiles can be used as inputs for training of social workers.

7 Discussion Events

H2020 National workshop "Challenge 6: Europe in a changing world", organized by FECYT (Foundation for Science and Technology)

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Rubén Fuentes Fernández https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6876-0979
Title	RAISD presentation
Place	Madrid
Year	2018
Type	Conference
Number, date	30/10/2018
Language	Spanish
Keywords	Forced migration, tailored attention and inclusion strategies, vulnerable people, vulnerability contexts, forcibly displaced people
Abstract	
<p>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and</p>	

data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.

RESCUE EU Project conference in Rome, organized by UNIMED

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Rubén Fuentes Fernández https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6876-0979
Title	RAISD project presentation
Place	Rome
Year	2019
Type	Conference
Number, date	12/09/2019
Language	English
Keywords	Forced migration, tailored attention and inclusion strategies, vulnerable people, vulnerability contexts, forcibly displaced people
Link(s)	https://www.uni-med.net/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/General-Assembly-Programme-Rome_PRINT-DEF.pdf

Abstract

Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-

ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.

Action Research and Unique Approaches in Refugee Studies – Horizon 2020 RAISD Project

Partner(s)	Anadolu University, Turkey
Author(s)	Prof. Dr. Erol Nezh Orhon
Title	Mültecilere Yönelik Çalışmalarda Eylem Araştırması ve Özgün Yaklaşımlar – Horizon 2020 RAISD Projesi
Place	Turkey
Year	2021
Type	Webinar Speech
Title	Anadolu University Faculty of Communication of Sciences' Webinar
Publisher	<i>Anadolu University</i>
Language	Turkish

RAISD Project Presentation at UNIMED SubNetwork Migration

Partner(s)	Anadolu University, Turkey
Author(s)	Prof. Dr. Erol Nezh Orhon
Place	Roma
Year	2021
Type	Webinar
Title	UNIMED SubNetwork Migration
Publisher	UNIMED
Language	English

Institute of Knowledge Technology (ITC) Conference

Partner(s)	UCM Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Spain
Author(s)	Rubén Fuentes Fernández https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6876-0979
Title	Presenting RAISD project
Place	Madrid
Year	2021
Type	Conference
Title	Institute of Knowledge Technology (ITC) Conference
Number, date	3/3/2021
Language	Spanish
Link(s)	https://youtu.be/EmhoHF6-O2Y

Abstract

Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and

data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.

RAISD (Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Forcibly Displaced People)

Partner(s)	Anadolu University, Turkey
Author(s)	Prof. Dr. Erol Nezh Orhon
Place	New York, United States
Year	30 June-8 July 2022
Type	Keynote Speaker
Title	University Refugees Act and Communicate for Health Project Conference
Publisher	The Center for Sustainable Development (CSD) at Columbia
Language	English
Keywords	Migrant health, social inclusion

8 Materials for dissemination activities

The project communication team established a RAISD **Press Office** to support media outreach, both general and international scientific, providing [clear project contacts](#), official [press-kit](#), e-Newsletters ([1](#) \ [2](#) \ [3](#) \ [4](#) \ [5](#) \ [6](#)); including other materials for dissemination activities, such as [Observatory poster](#), project brochure ([EN](#) – [IT](#) – [ES](#) – [HU](#) language versions), [Conference leaflet](#), [Roll-ups](#).

Screenshot 1. <https://raisd-h2020.eu/contacts/>

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fducm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

www.raisd-h2020.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

www.raisd-h2020.eu

Del. 9.8 Printed material with the project results [June, 2022]

Coordinator contact: Dr. Rubén Fuentes-Fernández | Universidad Complutense de Madrid | Calle del Profesor José García Santesmases, 9. Ciudad Universitaria 28040 MADRID, Spain
t: +34/91 394 7548 | e: rfuentes@ucm.es | w: www.ucm.es, grasia.fdi.ucm.es

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.